

OSCAR

Open Science Clusters' Action
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mTeSS-X Requirements

Deliverable D1: Requirements analysis based on the two TeSS instances
from ELIXIR and PaNOSC

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Introduction and scope

To overcome fragmentation of training resources across Research Infrastructures (RIs) and the Science Clusters, the [mTeSS-X project](#) aims to enhance the existing [ELIXIR TeSS platform](#) — to build an aggregator for training portals like ELIXIR TeSS and [PaNOSC training portals](#) — to natively support federation. Such a fully-featured open-source multi-tenanted training platform is expected to be an innovation for building a federation of portals to:

- help break down barriers between thematic communities,

- promote a more cohesive European research community,
- and promote FAIR and open training.

The project strives to support the federation of training catalogues using a multi-tenancy (multi-space) approach, and enabling cross-instance content exchange. This will allow RIs and their communities to maintain tailored catalogues with distinct identities, while simultaneously benefiting from a shared global pool of resources.

Scope of the deliverable

This document describes the requirements analysis, following the first two meetings of the focus group. In these meetings, the use cases of two TeSS instances from ELIXIR and PaNOSC were considered, with further input from project supporters. The user personas, user stories and requirements are described, followed by the metadata schema development plan.

Focus group meetings

Throughout the project, we are incorporating cooperative and iterative evaluation with users. To do this, we have formed a focus group of over 30 individuals from a broad range of domains including our formal project supporters and members, with contributions from Europe, Canada and Australia. So far, we have hosted two focus group meetings (described below), attended by the project members, supporters and the interested user groups such as OA5: Skills, Training, Rewards, Recognition & Upskilling of the EOSC-A. We have also arranged and attended several bespoke team meetings, and used various communication channels (i.e. mailing list and Slack) to discuss the requirements of our potential users. This user-centered design process allows us to capture the objective needs of the users to be able to build mTeSS-X as a tailored solution for our target audience.

Kick-off meeting (2024-11-01)

17 people attended the first focus group meeting where the project formally kicked off. Presentations were given to describe the implementation of the project, in terms of technical organisation, community, outreach, and engagement with EOSC. These were followed by interactive sessions to capture the user personas and user stories, clarify our definitions of “multi-spaces” and “exchange”, and to consider how we support cross-cutting metadata and branding. After the meeting, the captured information was used to define the first draft of the requirements.

Requirements gathering meeting (2025-01-13)

24 people attended the second focus group meeting where the draft of the requirements document was presented. Four activities took a section of the requirements each to identify and discuss any gaps and adjustments necessary. One notable item was the suggestion to look at academic publishing provenance as a model for sharing training materials between instances and spaces, for example, defining what to do if a training material is refreshed or revoked. After the meeting, the learnings were used to refine the requirements document.

User personas and user stories

This deliverable signposts user stories and personas to help to define users' needs and goals that will be answered through the behaviours of the training platform, providing context for how the software should function to meet those needs. They are critical components in ensuring that the development process aligns with the expectations of end-users.

Definitions of space and instance

Space

- A part within a deployment of TeSS.
- Each space will appear distinctive to the users and will have its own catalogue of materials and events.

Instance

- A deployment of TeSS where a group is responsible for technical operation.
- An instance will have one or more spaces.
- Examples: ELIXIR TeSS (RI: ELIXIR), PaNOSC (RI:PaNOSC), Taxila (RI: Netherlands), DReSA (RI: Australia)

Updated personas and stories for the project

The user and technical requirements for mTeSS-X are set out through the use of:

- **12 User Persona** - which tells us who are the users; and
- **15 User Stories** - which tells us what their desires are.

These personas vary in their skillset, their place in training development and the training life cycle and their agendas. The personas' skills may overlap. For example, a training

coordinator may also be a trainer and a trainee. A curator of a space may want to make their training available to other spaces and also discover training from other spaces.

For example: **Space Manager** will manage access and design for a space; **Space Curator** will manage content and metadata for materials.

User stories are high level requirements that could be translated later into the technical requirements for the framework. There are a number of user story templates. A common one is: **As a <role> I can <capability>, so that <receive benefit>**

For example: As a **trainer**
I can **see which materials are already available on a topic**
so that **I can improve my content and/or see what is missing.**

Organisation and details of the requirements

These will build on existing [ELIXIR TeSS](#) requirements and will overlap in their results. The different ways gather and derive requirements are organised into four groups:

- **Functional User Requirements** - which tells us what functions we need to support.
- **Non-functional User Requirements** - which tells us what community and documentation aspects we need to support.
- **Metadata Requirements** - the documentation (curation) and registration metadata within spaces and exchanging between them, needed to support a training lifecycle, FAIR principles and User Requirements.
- **Regulatory and Accessibility Requirements** - these are also functional requirements, however, we have separated them out to highlight the importance of continuing to build an accessible platform.

The full details of all these requirements are described in a living Google document, [mTeSS-X Requirements](#), and will be maintained as the project progresses. All requirements are **prioritised** using [MoSCoW](#) (Must have, Should have, Could have, Will not have).

Metadata schema development

Based on the current metadata properties, an initial schema for the mTeSS-X project will be developed on the basis of currently available metadata schemas in the area of training materials and made available on GitHub for discussion. Interested stakeholders can participate in the discussion and development of the schema on the basis of GitHub issues.

The hypothetical exchange of the schemes between mTeSS-X instances is simulated via user stories and sequence diagrams in order to cover as many use cases as possible (e.g. different Schema versions of mTeSS-X instances) in advance and to recognise problems at an early stage.

Releases of the developed schema are planned as soon as parts of the schema to be developed for mTeSS-X have been developed with the community. The current schema is published on [Schemas.science](https://schemas.science). A developed schema release will be embedded in the current mTeSS-X development instances as soon as possible.

Conclusions and next steps

The mTeSS-X project represents a significant advancement in the federation of training catalogues across scientific domains, Research Infrastructures and training portals. Through a user-centered design process, the project has successfully gathered insights from diverse stakeholders, ensuring that the developed platform aligns with real-world needs of both trainers and trainees. The structured approach to defining user personas and user stories has provided a strong foundation for identifying practical user requirements. Additionally, the emphasis on metadata schema development underscores the project's commitment to interoperability and sustainable data exchange.

Looking ahead, we intend to continue active engagement with the diverse user community to build on the existing collection of user requirements, update the users and take regular feedback post implementation. This will be done via the focus group meetings to be held every three months throughout the duration of the project. The next meeting scheduled for 2025-04-08 will provide a demonstration of the progress made thus far about multi-spaces feature implementation and gather feedback from the community. In the meeting, we also plan to get an update on the metadata exchange work, and have discussions about curation of the content.